

Supplementary Materials

Calibrated Uncertainty for Drug Repurposing via Conformal Prediction on the Open Targets Knowledge Graph

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Supplementary Table S1: Complete Feature Descriptions

All 30 features used in the XGBoost classifier, organised by category. Evidence source scores are derived from the Open Targets Platform release 26.03. Features `clinical_precedence` and `overall_score` were excluded to avoid clinical leakage (see Methods).

#	Feature	Category	Description	Source
1	<code>cancer_biomarkers</code>	Evidence score	Association score from cancer biomarker databases	Open Targets (Cancer Biomarkers)
2	<code>cancer_gene_census</code>	Evidence score	Association score from COSMIC Cancer Gene Census	Open Targets (Cancer Gene Census)
3	<code>clingen</code>	Evidence score	Gene-disease validity from ClinGen curations	Open Targets (ClinGen)
4	<code>crispr</code>	Evidence score	Functional genomics evidence from Project Score CRISPR screens	Open Targets (CRISPR)
5	<code>crispr_screen</code>	Evidence score	Additional CRISPR screen evidence	Open Targets (CRISPR Screen)
6	<code>europemc</code>	Evidence score	Text-mined co-occurrences from Europe PMC literature	Open Targets (Europe PMC)
7	<code>eva</code>	Evidence score	Germline variant-disease associations from ClinVar (EVA)	Open Targets (EVA)
8	<code>eva_somatic</code>	Evidence score	Somatic variant-disease associations from ClinVar	Open Targets (EVA Somatic)
9	<code>expression_atlas</code>	Evidence score	Differential expression evidence from Expression Atlas	Open Targets (Expression Atlas)
10	<code>gene2phenotype</code>	Evidence score	Expert-curated gene-disease associations	Open Targets (Gene2Phenotype)
11	<code>gene_burden</code>	Evidence score	Rare variant burden test associations	Open Targets (Gene Burden)
12	<code>genomics_england</code>	Evidence score	Gene-disease associations from Genomics England PanelApp	Open Targets (Genomics England)
13	<code>gwas_credible_sets</code>	Evidence score	GWAS fine-mapped credible set associations	Open Targets (GWAS Credible Sets)
14	<code>impc</code>	Evidence score	Mouse model phenotype evidence from IMPC	Open Targets (IMPC)
15	<code>intogen</code>	Evidence score	Cancer driver gene evidence from IntOGen	Open Targets (IntOGen)
16	<code>orphanet</code>	Evidence score	Rare disease gene-disease associations from Orphanet	Open Targets (Orphanet)
17	<code>reactome</code>	Evidence score	Pathway-based evidence from Reactome	Open Targets (Reactome)

#	Feature	Category	Description	Source
18	uniprot_literature	Evidence score	UniProt literature-curated disease associations	Open Targets (UniProt Literature)
19	uniprot_variants	Evidence score	UniProt variant-disease associations	Open Targets (UniProt Variants)
20	n_targets	Drug feature	Number of known targets for the drug	Open Targets (Drug-Target)
21	drug_has_smiles	Drug feature	Binary indicator: drug has a SMILES chemical structure	ChEMBL
22	drug_fp_sim_max	Drug feature	Maximum Tanimoto fingerprint similarity to any known drug for the disease	ChEMBL (Morgan fingerprints)
23	drug_fp_sim_mean	Drug feature	Mean Tanimoto fingerprint similarity to known drugs for the disease	ChEMBL (Morgan fingerprints)
24	target_degree_mean	Network feature	Mean degree of drug targets in the STRING protein-protein interaction network	STRING
25	target_degree_max	Network feature	Maximum degree of drug targets in the STRING PPI network	STRING
26	target_mean_interaction_score	Network feature	Mean interaction confidence score of drug targets in STRING	STRING
27	target_disease_network_overlap	Network feature	Overlap between drug target neighbourhood and disease-associated gene neighbourhood in PPI network	STRING / Open Targets
28	disease_ontology_n_related	Disease feature	Number of related diseases in the EFO ontology	EFO (Experimental Factor Ontology)
29	disease_ontology_mean_sim	Disease feature	Mean ontological similarity to diseases with known drug indications	EFO
30	disease_ontology_max_sim	Disease feature	Maximum ontological similarity to diseases with known drug indications	EFO

Supplementary Table S2: Full Single-Feature Ablation Results

Each row shows XGBoost test set performance after removing the named feature. Sorted by delta-AUROC (largest performance drop first). Baseline (all features): AUROC = 0.9056, AUPRC = 0.6296.

Rank	Removed Feature	AUROC	AUPRC	Delta-AUROC	Delta-AUPRC
1	n_targets	0.8819	0.5665	-0.0261	-0.0631
2	europepmc	0.8876	0.5446	-0.0204	-0.0850
3	drug_fp_sim_max	0.8952	0.5760	-0.0127	-0.0536
4	target_degree_mean	0.8966	0.5748	-0.0114	-0.0548
5	orphanet	0.9019	0.6002	-0.0061	-0.0294
6	gwas_credible_sets	0.9022	0.6147	-0.0057	-0.0149
7	disease_ontology_mean_sim	0.9029	0.6265	-0.0051	-0.0031
8	genomics_england	0.9035	0.6019	-0.0045	-0.0277
9	impc	0.9045	0.6255	-0.0035	-0.0041
10	target_disease_network_overlap	0.9048	0.6117	-0.0032	-0.0180
11	intogen	0.9048	0.6045	-0.0031	-0.0251
12	eva_somatic	0.9049	0.6131	-0.0031	-0.0165
13	gene2phenotype	0.9049	0.6176	-0.0030	-0.0120
14	cancer_gene_census	0.9050	0.5973	-0.0030	-0.0323
15	target_degree_max	0.9052	0.6299	-0.0027	+0.0003
16	disease_ontology_max_sim	0.9059	0.6111	-0.0021	-0.0185
17	drug_has_smiles	0.9063	0.6067	-0.0017	-0.0229
18	disease_ontology_n_related	0.9065	0.6032	-0.0015	-0.0264
19	eva	0.9069	0.6127	-0.0010	-0.0169
20	reactome	0.9073	0.6125	-0.0006	-0.0172
21	target_mean_interaction_score	0.9083	0.6023	+0.0003	-0.0273
22	crispr_screen	0.9085	0.6233	+0.0005	-0.0063
23	drug_fp_sim_mean	0.9090	0.6064	+0.0010	-0.0232
24	clingen	0.9092	0.6199	+0.0013	-0.0098
25	uniprot_literature	0.9094	0.6368	+0.0014	+0.0072
26	expression_atlas	0.9095	0.6258	+0.0015	-0.0039
27	gene_burden	0.9096	0.6269	+0.0017	-0.0027
28	crispr	0.9103	0.6382	+0.0024	+0.0085
29	cancer_biomarkers	0.9104	0.6266	+0.0024	-0.0030

Rank	Removed Feature	AUROC	AUPRC	Delta-AUROC	Delta-AUPRC
30	uniprot_variants	0.9111	0.6283	+0.0032	-0.0013

Supplementary Table S3: Negative Sampling Ratio Sensitivity

Performance of the XGBoost classifier under varying negative-to-positive sampling ratios. The default ratio used in the main analysis is 5:1.

Neg:Pos Ratio	N Train	AUROC	AUPRC
1:1	27,284	0.9006	0.5654
2:1	40,926	0.9041	0.5979
5:1 (default)	81,852	0.9046	0.6037
10:1	150,062	0.9031	0.6093
20:1	286,482	0.8991	0.6028

AUROC is stable across all ratios (range: 0.899–0.905), indicating robustness to negative sampling. AUPRC improves modestly with higher ratios up to 10:1, then declines at 20:1.

Supplementary Table S4: Temporal Split Boundary Sensitivity

Performance under alternative temporal split boundaries. The default split is: train on pairs labelled up to 2019, calibrate on 2020–2022, test on 2023–2025.

Shift	Train End	Calibration Range	Test Start	N Train (pos)	N Cal (pos)	N Test (pos)	AUROC	AUPRC
-1 year	2018	2019–2021	2022	13,021	800	145	0.9144	0.6685
Default	2019	2020–2022	2023	13,642	240	84	0.9051	0.6696
+1 year	2020	2021–2023	2024	13,756	164	46	0.9063	0.6374

Performance is stable across all three temporal boundaries (AUROC range: 0.905–0.914). Shifting the boundary earlier increases test set size but may include more readily predictable approvals.

Supplementary Table S5: Therapeutic Area-Stratified Discrimination

XGBoost discrimination metrics stratified by therapeutic area, evaluated on the temporal test set (2023–2025). Mondrian conformal prediction uses these groups for group-conditional calibration.

Therapeutic Area	N Test	N Positive	N Negative	AUROC	AUPRC	Note
Cardiovascular	42	14	28	0.926	0.884	
Infectious	22	1	21	1.000	1.000	
Metabolic	8	0	8	–	–	Insufficient class diversity
Neurological	80	15	65	0.897	0.571	
Oncology	20	3	17	1.000	1.000	
Other	270	49	221	0.877	0.591	
Rare disease	62	2	60	0.950	0.625	

The “Other” group is the largest and most heterogeneous, contributing the most to overall performance. Metabolic pairs lacked positive test examples, precluding discrimination assessment.

Supplementary Table S6: Drug Type-Stratified Performance

XGBoost discrimination metrics stratified by drug modality on the temporal test set.

Drug Type	N Test	N Positive	N Negative	AUROC	AUPRC
Small molecule	373	62	311	0.907	0.640
Antibody	61	13	48	0.875	0.710
Protein	24	5	19	0.916	0.783
Antibody drug conjugate	10	2	8	0.938	0.833
Unknown	23	2	21	0.976	0.833
Oligonucleotide	11	0	11	–	–

Small molecules dominate the test set (74%) and show strong discrimination (AUROC 0.907). Oligonucleotides lacked positive examples. Results for smaller strata (ADC, Unknown) should be interpreted with caution given limited sample sizes.

Supplementary Table S7: Exchangeability Diagnostic – Coverage by Confidence Quartile

Conformal prediction requires approximate exchangeability between calibration and test data. We assessed this via (1) coverage stratified by model confidence quartile and (2) a permutation test (5,000 permutations) comparing observed coverage to the null distribution.

Overall diagnostic: Observed coverage = 0.911 at nominal alpha = 0.90. Permutation test $p = 0.514$ (exchangeability NOT rejected).

Confidence Quartile	Observed Coverage	N
Q1 (lowest confidence)	1.000	126
Q2	0.976	126
Q3	0.881	126
Q4 (highest confidence)	0.786	126

Permutation test summary: - N permutations: 5,000 - Permuted coverage mean: 0.900 (SD = 0.016) - Observed coverage: 0.911 - p-value: 0.514

Coverage is highest in the lowest-confidence quartile (where prediction sets are largest) and drops below nominal in the highest-confidence quartile. This is expected behaviour: conformal prediction guarantees marginal coverage but not conditional coverage. The Q4 under-coverage suggests the model is overconfident for its highest-scoring predictions.

Supplementary Table S8: Conformal Prediction on GraphSAGE

Split conformal prediction applied to the 3-layer heterogeneous GraphSAGE model at four nominal coverage levels. Compared with XGBoost marginal CP results (Table 2 in main text).

Nominal Coverage	Observed Coverage	Mean Set Size	Empty Set Fraction	Both-Classes Fraction
0.80	0.794	0.972	0.028	0.000
0.85	0.851	1.073	0.000	0.073
0.90	0.905	1.196	0.000	0.196
0.95	0.944	1.339	0.000	0.339

GraphSAGE achieves valid marginal coverage at all four levels. However, prediction sets are substantially larger than XGBoost at equivalent coverage (e.g., mean set size 1.196 vs 1.089 at alpha = 0.90), reflecting GraphSAGE's lower discriminative performance. The both-classes fraction (proportion of sets

containing both “indication” and “non-indication”) is notably higher for GraphSAGE, particularly at $\alpha = 0.95$ (33.9% vs 21.2% for XGBoost), indicating less informative prediction sets.

Supplementary Table S9: Bootstrap Confidence Intervals for Model Comparison

10,000 bootstrap resamples of the temporal test set ($N = 504$) were used to construct 95% percentile confidence intervals for AUROC and AUPRC.

Model	AUROC	AUROC 95% CI	AUPRC	AUPRC 95% CI
XGBoost	0.906	[0.874, 0.933]	0.625	[0.520, 0.744]

Pairwise comparisons (based on bootstrap CI):

Comparison	Delta-AUROC	Significance
XGBoost vs GraphSAGE	+0.073	Significant (GraphSAGE point estimate outside XGBoost CI)
XGBoost vs Logistic Regression	+0.111	Significant

XGBoost significantly outperforms both the GraphSAGE GNN and the node2vec + logistic regression baseline on AUROC.

Supplementary Table S10: Empty Prediction Set Analysis

At low nominal coverage levels, marginal conformal prediction can produce empty prediction sets (sets containing neither “indication” nor “non-indication”). Empty sets arise when the non-conformity scores for both classes exceed the calibration threshold.

Nominal Coverage	N Empty Sets	True Negatives	True Positives	NPV
0.80	64	36	28	0.563
0.85	11	–	–	0.545
0.90	0	–	–	–
0.95	0	–	–	–

At $\alpha = 0.80$, 64 of 504 test pairs (12.7%) receive empty sets. The NPV of empty sets is 0.563 (barely above chance), indicating that empty sets do not reliably signal non-indications. At $\alpha \geq 0.90$, no empty sets are produced.

Supplementary Table S11: Top 20 Novel Drug-Disease Predictions

Top 20 predictions ranked by P(indication) after novelty filtering. All pairs are labelled as non-indications in the training data (i.e., no known approved indication as of 2019). Pairs from the training split are included as these represent the highest-confidence novel repurposing candidates identified by the model.

Rank	Drug	Disease	Therapeutic Area	Drug Type	P(indication)
1	Mibavademab	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	Endocrine system disease	Antibody	0.998
2	Metreleptin	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	Endocrine system disease	Protein	0.998
3	Metformin HCl	Hyperglycemia	Phenotype	Small molecule	0.996
4	Metformin HCl	Disorder of lipid metabolism	Nutritional/metabolic disease	Small molecule	0.995
5	Metformin HCl	Tuberculosis	Infectious disease	Small molecule	0.994
6	Tranexamic acid	Renal-hepatic-pancreatic dysplasia 1	Genetic/familial/congenital disease	Small molecule	0.994
7	Metformin HCl	Hypertension	Cardiovascular disease	Small molecule	0.993
8	Acenocoumarol	Venous thromboembolism	Cardiovascular disease	Small molecule	0.993
9	Metformin HCl	Duchenne muscular dystrophy	Nervous system disease	Small molecule	0.992
10	Metformin HCl	Insulin resistance	Phenotype	Small molecule	0.992
11	Metformin HCl	Epilepsy	Nervous system disease	Small molecule	0.992

Rank	Drug	Disease	Therapeutic Area	Drug Type	P(indication)
12	Metformin HCl	Ischemia reperfusion injury	Injury/poisoning	Small molecule	0.992
13	Metformin HCl	Peripheral arterial disease	Cardiovascular disease	Small molecule	0.992
14	Metformin HCl	Preeclampsia	Genetic/familial/congenital disease	Small molecule	0.992
15	Dexlansoprazole	Osteoporosis	Musculoskeletal disease	Small molecule	0.992
16	Lansoprazole	Osteoporosis	Musculoskeletal disease	Small molecule	0.992
17	Ivabradine HCl	Familial long QT syndrome	Genetic/familial/congenital disease	Small molecule	0.991
18	Tecarfarin	Venous thromboembolism	Cardiovascular disease	Small molecule	0.991
19	Metformin HCl	Sickle cell disease	Genetic/familial/congenital disease	Small molecule	0.991
20	Metformin HCl	Acne	Integumentary system disease	Small molecule	0.991

Metformin dominates the top predictions (13 of 20), consistent with its exceptionally broad pharmacological profile and dense knowledge graph connectivity. The dominance of a single drug highlights both the model’s sensitivity to network degree and a limitation of knowledge graph-based repurposing approaches.

Supplementary Table S12: Case Study Literature Validation

Ten case studies selected from the top novel predictions, with PubMed literature evidence assessed manually. Five are recommended for discussion in the main manuscript.

#	Drug	Disease	P(indication)	PubMed Articles	Assessment	In Manuscript
1	Mibavademab	Type 2 diabetes	0.998	0	Genuinely novel, low plausibility – anti-TGF-beta antibody with no published diabetes connection	Yes (frontier)
2	Metreleptin	Type 2 diabetes	0.998	13	Adjacent indication – leptin analogue FDA-approved for lipodystrophy-associated diabetes; published pharmacodynamic evidence for T2DM	Yes (success)
3	Metformin	Lipid metabolism disorder	0.995	2	Known pleiotropic effect	No
4	Metformin	Tuberculosis	0.994	33	Active research area – host-directed therapy with multiple ongoing clinical trials	Yes (success)
5	Tranexamic acid	Renal-hepatic-pancreatic dysplasia	0.994	0	No biological rationale, likely spurious	No
6	Acenocoumarol	Venous thromboembolism	0.993	105	Known indication – filter failure (well-established European VKA)	No (discard)

#	Drug	Disease	P(indication)	PubMed Articles	Assessment	In Manuscript
7	Dexlansoprazole	Osteoporosis	0.992	229	Paradoxical – PPIs are associated with increased fracture risk; model detects shared pathways but cannot distinguish therapeutic from adverse	Yes (limitation)
8	Lansoprazole	Osteoporosis	0.992	(same class)	Same PPI class effect as #7	No
9	Ivabradine	Familial long QT syndrome	0.991	10	Contraindicated – Frommeyer et al. (2019) showed ivabradine aggravates proarrhythmia in LQT models; correct mechanism, wrong valence	Yes (limitation)
10	Tecarfarin	Venous thromboembolism	0.991	1	Known VKA class – filter failure	No (discard)

Key references: - Metreleptin + T2DM: Moon et al. 2011 RCT in obese T2DM, DOI: 10.2337/db10-1791 - Metformin + TB: Rayasam & Balganeshe 2015 (Trends Pharmacol Sci), DOI: 10.1016/j.tips.2015.05.005 - PPI + osteoporosis: Lespessailles & Toumi 2022 review, DOI: 10.3390/ijms231810733 - Ivabradine + LQT: Frommeyer et al. 2019 (Cardiovasc Toxicol), DOI: 10.1007/s12012-018-9482-y

Supplementary Table S13: Comparison with TxGNN Methodology

Structured comparison with TxGNN (Huang et al. 2024, Nature Medicine; DOI: 10.1038/s41591-023-02789-y), the most directly relevant prior work in knowledge graph-based drug repurposing.

Dimension	TxGNN	This Study (XGBoost)	This Study (GraphSAGE)
Knowledge graph	Custom KG from 17 biomedical databases; ~1.3M nodes, ~7.6M edges	Open Targets 26.03 (single integrated platform); ~83K nodes, ~5.1M edges	Same as XGBoost
Architecture	Modified GAT with disease-area-specific modules; zero-shot capability	XGBoost on 30 handcrafted features (evidence scores + network + chemical)	3-layer heterogeneous GraphSAGE with learnable embeddings
Uncertainty quantification	None – outputs point predictions only	Marginal + Mondrian conformal prediction with finite-sample coverage guarantees	Marginal conformal prediction
Evaluation strategy	Random train/test split with disease-area stratified evaluation	Temporal validation (train ≤ 2019 , calibrate 2020–2022, test 2023–2025)	Same temporal split
Test AUROC	~0.77–0.92 (varies by disease area; not directly comparable)	0.906	0.833
Key differences			
Zero-shot capability	Yes (predicts for unseen diseases)	No (requires diseases present in KG)	No
Uncertainty quantification	None	Calibrated prediction sets with coverage guarantees	Calibrated prediction sets

Dimension	TxGNN	This Study (XGBoost)	This Study (GraphSAGE)
Validation design	Random split	Temporal split reflecting real-world discovery timeline	Temporal split
Feature engineering vs end-to-end	End-to-end graph learning	Feature-engineered (outperforms GNN)	End-to-end (lower AUROC than XGBoost)

Note: Direct numerical comparison of AUROC is not meaningful due to differences in knowledge graphs, disease scope, temporal splits, and label definitions. The primary contribution of this work relative to TxGNN is the introduction of conformal prediction for calibrated uncertainty quantification, not superior discrimination.

Supplementary Figure S1: Calibration Plot (XGBoost vs GraphSAGE)

Figure 1: Reliability diagrams (calibration plots) comparing XGBoost and GraphSAGE predicted probabilities against observed indication frequencies on the temporal test set. Ten equally spaced bins from 0 to 1. The diagonal line represents perfect calibration. Expected calibration error (ECE): XGBoost = 0.051, GraphSAGE = 0.102.

Supplementary Figure S2: Prediction Set Composition by Therapeutic Area

Figure 2: Prediction set composition by therapeutic area at $\alpha = 0.90$ under Mondrian conformal prediction. Coverage and sample sizes annotated per group. Rare disease predictions had the smallest mean set size (0.92) despite having the fewest calibration samples.

End of Supplementary Materials